

Mass Spectral Study of 2-Mercapto-pyrimidines

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The Mass Spectral study of a set of seven 1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-1-(substituted)-pyrimidine-2-thiols have shown a consistent behaviour ; involving loss of SH, CH₃ from gemdimethyl, retro-Diels-Alder and scissions along a, b, c, d, e, f, g, and h. In 2'-nitro-aryl-pyrimidines the peaks corresponding to (M-OH)⁺, (M-O)⁺ and (M-NO)⁺ are absent.

THE present study describes the mass spectral pattern¹ of a set of seven 2-mercapto-pyrimidines (Fig. 1; Ia-g). 2-Mercaptopyrimidines have shown a consistent behaviour involving loss of SH, CH₃

Fig. 1

Ia, R=CH₃; Ib, R=C₆H₅; Ic, R=o-NH₂-C₆H₄;
Id, R=p-NH₂-C₆H₄; Ie, R=o-CH₃CONH-C₆H₄;
If, R=o-NO₂-C₆H₄; Ig, R=2-CH₃-6-NO₂-C₆H₃

from gemdimethyl, retro-Diels-Alder and scissions along a, b, c, d, e, f, g, and h (Chart 1). The loss of RN from I have not been noticed.

The mercaptopyrimidines from which the peaks are obtained, are mentioned under every mass ion peak.

Every 2-mercaptopyrimidine along with common modes of fragmentations (Chart 1) also have some characteristic modes of fragmentations.

1,4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(methyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ia; Table 1): The molecular ion m/e 170 undergoes retro-Diels-Alder and also loses SH giving rise to ion peaks m/e 111 and 137 (Chart 2).

1,4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(phenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ib; Table 1): The ion peak m/e 150 obtained after the fragmentation of Ib along "d" undergoes further fragmentation giving rise to ion peaks m/e 77, 91 and 118. The ion peak m/e 232 undergoes retro-Diels-Alder in a similar manner as in case of Ia, giving rise to ion peaks m/e 173. The loss of SH from Ib have not been noticed. The ion peak m/e 232 loses H and then undergoes fragmentation giving rise to ion peak m/e 149.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(o-aminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ie; Table 1): The ion peak m/e

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247 loses \dot{H} and then undergoes retro-Diels-Alder giving rise to ion peak m/e 187. Also ion peak m/e 133 obtained from m/e 232 by fragmentation along "f" undergoes further fragmentation giving rise to ion peak m/e 132, 131, 91 and 41. Ion peaks m/e 132, 131, 91 arises due to the presence of NH_2 group on the phenyl ring.

1,4-Dihydro-4, 4,6-trimethyl-1-(p-aminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Id; Table I): The ion peak m/e 165 is obtained by the fragmentation of m/e 247 along "d" which undergoes further fragmentation giving rise to ion peaks m/e 133, 132, 131, 92, 91, 106 and 105. The molecular ion peak loses \dot{H} and then undergoes retro-Diels-Alder by the loss of HSCN giving rise to ion peak m/e 187.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(o-acetylaminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ie; Table I): The mercaptopyrimidine (Ie) gave molecular ion peak m/e 289, which loses CH_3 and NCO successively giving rise to ion peaks m/e 274 and 232. The molecular ion peak m/e 289 also loses $COCH_3$ giving rise to ion peak m/e 246 which then undergoes retro-Diels-Alder giving rise to ion peak m/e 187. The ion peak m/e 274 undergoes fragmentation along "f" giving rise to ion peak m/e 175. The ion peak m/e 175 then undergoes fragmentation giving rise to ion peak m/e 132 and 131.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(o-nitrophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (If; Table I): The ion peak m/e 277 loses NO_2 and SH giving rise to ion peaks m/e 231 and 244. It is interesting to note that in case of If the losses of NO_2 and SH have been noticed but in case of Ib, Ic, Id and Ie this type of loss have not been noticed.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(2'-nitro-o-tolyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ig; Table I): It is interesting to note that mercaptopyrimidine (Ig) did not give molecular ion peak at m/e 291 (M^+), but all other mercaptopyrimidines (Ia-f) gave corresponding molecular ion peaks. The highest ion peak m/e 276 is obtained by the loss of $\dot{C}H_3$ from the parent molecule. The ion peak ($M - NO_2$)⁺ m/e 245 in case of Ig is similar to ion peak ($M - NO_2$)⁺ m/e 231 in case of If. Also the loss of SH from the ion peak m/e 276 ($M - \dot{C}H_3$) is similar to the loss of SH from ion peak m/e 277 in case of If.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Micro-analyses are by CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra were run in KBr wafers on a Perkin-Elmer infracord-137 spectrophotometer and mass spectra were on a Varian Mat CH-7 spectrophotometer. The mass spectra were run under the following experimental

TABLE I—MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINES* (Ia-g)

Sr. No.	Ia		Ib		Ic		Id		Ie		If		Ig	
	m/e	(%)												
1.	170	(10)	232	(82)	247	(100)	247	(49)	289	(100)	277	(39)	276	(29)
2.	156	(55)	231	(12)	246	(5)	246	(6)	279	(41)	262	(13)	246	(27)
3.	155	(100)	209	(19)	232	(88)	233	(16)	274	(38)	244	(9)	245	(100)
4.	141	(44)	218	(50)	187	(6)	232	(100)	246	(10)	281	(61)	243	(10)
5.	137	(25)	217	(100)	174	(50)	198	(8)	232	(92)	218	(8)	231	(5)
6.	115	(14)	173	(12)	173	(88)	187	(5)	187	(17)	217	(24)	217	(12)
7.	114	(67)	167	(46)	158	(24)	173	(14)	175	(11)	167	(73)	197	(9)
8.	113	(47)	158	(38)	145	(26)	165	(7)	174	(24)	163	(11)	189	(7)
9.	111	(20)	150	(17)	133	(90)	149	(6)	173	(56)	151	(48)	167	(29)
10.	100	(17)	149	(70)	132	(87)	133	(9)	167	(69)	149	(100)	165	(57)
11.	99	(40)	118	(15)	131	(83)	132	(15)	150	(25)	137	(24)	149	(66)
12.	97	(33)	114	(22)	104	(21)	131	(13)	149	(90)	125	(23)	114	(28)
13.	96	(13)	113	(16)	99	(28)	125	(7)	133	(45)	123	(22)	111	(33)
14.	82	(23)	99	(9)	92	(80)	124	(11)	132	(42)	122	(9)	97	(48)
15.	81	(39)	97	(31)	91	(23)	118	(7)	131	(15)	114	(45)	96	(21)
16.	71	(43)	96	(15)	90	(50)	107	(8)	114	(5)	111	(46)	95	(39)
17.	70	(26)	95	(25)	77	(37)	106	(10)	113	(30)	109	(40)	83	(50)
18.	69	(39)	94	(37)	65	(78)	105	(9)	99	(10)	99	(18)	82	(27)
19.	57	(80)	92	(42)	64	(35)	99	(5)	97	(39)	97	(59)	81	(61)
20.	56	(34)	91	(12)	56	(20)	92	(15)	96	(15)	96	(29)	71	(52)
21.	55	(74)	88	(31)	55	(81)	91	(22)	95	(31)	95	(84)	70	(39)
22.	42	(30)	82	(19)	42	(58)	82	(9)	83	(37)	83	(57)	69	(50)
23.	41	(54)	81	(24)	41	(83)	81	(7)	82	(16)	82	(29)	57	(60)
24.	—	—	77	(34)	39	(64)	65	(6)	81	(27)	81	(54)	55	(52)
25.	—	—	71	(37)	—	—	64	(31)	71	(45)	71	(63)	43	(57)
26.	—	—	70	(26)	—	—	52	(7)	70	(35)	70	(47)	41	(44)
27.	—	—	69	(32)	—	—	42	(11)	69	(37)	69	(56)	—	—
28.	—	—	66	(50)	—	—	41	(14)	57	(51)	57	(68)	—	—
29.	—	—	55	(33)	—	—	—	—	55	(42)	55	(57)	—	—
30.	—	—	42	(16)	—	—	—	—	43	(45)	43	(60)	—	—
31.	—	—	41	(31)	—	—	—	—	42	(9)	42	(17)	—	—
32.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	41	(31)	41	(43)	—	—

* Values given in brackets represents the relative abundance of the corresponding mass ions. Values underlined show the base ion peak.

conditions : inlet temperature 80°, ionising voltage 70ev and ion current 100 μ A.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(methyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ia)² ; 1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(phenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ib)² ; 1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(*o*-aminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol³ (Ic) ; 1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-1-(*o*-acetylaminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ie)⁴ ; 1,4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(*o*-nitrophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (If)³ and 1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(2'-nitro-*o*-tolyl)pyrimidine-2-thiol (Ig)³ were prepared by the methods reported earlier.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(*p*-aminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Id) : 1,4-Dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol⁵ was prepared by the condensation of *p*-nitroaniline with 2-methyl-2-isothiocyano-4-pentanone using protonic catalyst.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol was reduced to 1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(*p*-aminophenyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (Id) by using SnCl₂/HCl as a reducing agent³. Yield 1.800 gm (74%). m.p. 210°. Found, C, 63, 27 ; H, 7.01 ; N, 16.85 ; C₁₃H₁₇N₃S requires C, 63.16 ; H, 6.88 ; N, 17.00%.

The IR spectrum of Id shows a band at 3400 cm⁻¹ showing the presence of NH₂ group. The mass spectrum gave a molecular ion peak at m/e 277.

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